

Book Review

Jeff Knaebel, *Experiments in Moral Sovereignty: Notes of an American Exile*, Friends of Gandhi Museum, Pune, 2006, pp. 230 +x; price. Rs. 325.

The year 2006 marked the 100th anniversary of the commencement of Gandhi's Satyagraha addressing truth and non-violence. Since then his teaching example has spread round the world. Today, many Americans are attempting to live by his principles. One them is Jeff Knaebel, a member of Friends of Gandhi Museum living in Pune. The book reviewed here is his first, in which he presents his case for expatriation from his country of birth.

The book expresses three main themes:

(1) A call to people of the world to generate an evolutionary quantum leap into a higher consciousness of nonviolence in order that we may survive as a species. This call is for a revolution from fear to love, from greed to generosity, from cruelty to compassion, from deceit to truth, from dependence to self reliance, from war to peace, from corporate enslavement to individual liberty.

(2) An appeal to India to help raise humanity to a more sacred destiny – not as a nation state, but as a people - to guidehu mankind to that spiritual unity which alone can bring peace on earth.

(3) The story of one man's quest for individual moral sovereignty in a world of institutionalized structural violence imposed by the corporate warfare state. This struggle - within himself as well as with powers that be – led him to the renunciation of and severance from his native land.

The book offers a set of simple yet horrifying observations. During most of the past century, USA has been engaged in foreign warfare. Within the past century, nation states have murdered at least 200 million people in wars and internal conflict. The modern corporate warfare state has wrought such vast wanton ecological and cultural destruction as to threaten survival of human species. We live under threat of an insane political theory of nuclear deterrence through mutually assured destruction.

The book attempts to describe what the State really is and how it actually operates, stripped of propaganda and delusion. It points out the

fatal ethical design errors of system. It shows how power structures attract the most corruptible of men: those who will to ruthless murder in order to accomplish their evil ends. At the peak of its growth cycle, the State becomes a gang of criminals ruling by a mix of force, deceit and manufactured consent. Gandhi is quoted, "The individual has a soul, but as the State is a soulless machine, it can never be weaned from the violence to which it owes its very existence."

Using Gandhi's demonstration of means is to end as seed is to tree, it is shown how an institution based upon the fundamental moral flaw of a monopoly on violence can never lead to peace. The State is likened to a machine which has run amok - out of control. The relevant operational fact is that State-sponsored endless war is no more than a profiteering racket. War is health of State. War is profit to the big corporate money interests. Loss of life does not report to the corporate balance sheet.

The nature of power relations which create the operating dynamics of the State is examined. The author concludes: "For power, there is no tomorrow. There are no grandchildren. Even of earth, there is none. There is only power." The relationship of individual to State is examined. How did it come to be? Is it a valid relationship in terms of reason, law, common sense, and conscience? The author asks basic questions of the State and his relationship to it. Does it murder? Am I financing this murder? Am I therefore responsible? Do I finance murder voluntarily? Am I therefore a slave?

Perceiving the American state to be a criminal operation of nigh incomprehensible scale - having perpetrated innumerable heinous crimes against humanity - and having executed no contract by which it has any jurisdiction over his life, Jeff Knaebel declares his right to renounce and depart from it without obligation. He presents for our consideration a personal Declaration of Severance and Independence from the United States. It says in part: I hold these to be self evident truths, that all people are endowed at birth with equal, inalienable and independent rights, among which are sole possession of their own life, liberty and the seeking of happiness in their own way. That men may secure these rights by forming such associations as they choose, which must operate by non-coerced full consensus, and from which any member is free to secede.

Gandhi's example of Satyagraha (strong adherence to truth) with Ahimsa (non-violence) points the method. "We must be the change we wish to see." A simple first step is to tell the truth in every transaction,

to every person, at all times, in every situation. When we begin to call things by their true name – for example, “collateral damage” is murder pure and simple – we will begin to wake up to the reality of the human condition created by *The Powers That Be*.

He concludes that there is no political institution/ism, no authoritarian person, no economic policy, and no government that can save us from the self-inflicted disaster bearing down upon us. Only the freedom to be in love with life - and to express that love in person to person natural relationship - can save us. This is a freedom to live in the original unconditioned character that is found deep within each of us - of total, s weeping, deep, overflowing, unconditional love of life, of this earth, of its creatures, of ourselves, of each other. He feels that to express this love, we must get the State out of our way. The book with its clarity of thought, passionate commitment and provocative insights is recommended for all the activists and alternative visionaries.

The book is available at a discounted price of rupees 150/- from <www.otherindiabookstore.com>.

Delia Thomas

Peter Broks, *Understanding Popular Science*, Open University Press: Berlhire, 2006, pp. 188 + xii,

This book on popular science is a series in Cultural and Media Studies, that aims to “facilitate a diverse range of critical investigations into pressing questions considered to be central to current thinking and research.” (p. x). The authors reminds us in the introduction that the culture we live is “saturated with science.” He goes to the extent of saying that science might be taken as the “defining feature of modern world.” (p. 1).

In fact popular science is where most of us make sense of the facts of science. *Understanding Popular Science* provides a framework to help us appreciate the development of popular science and current debates about it. Peter Broks shows how popular science has been invented, redefined and fought over. From early nineteenth century’s radical science to twenty-first century of government initiatives, the author examines popular science as an arena where “the authority of science and the authority of state are legitimized and challenged.”

The book contains seven chapters, including “Uncertain Times,” “Progress and Professionalism” and “Science and Modernity.” The last

chapter is particularly insightful. In the section dealing with science and democracy, the author asserts: "It has taken centuries of cultural, social, economic and political struggle to develop the mechanisms and institutions that enable the sharing of power in a *democratic* society... We should, perhaps, expect an equally long struggle to develop the cultural, social, economic and political machinery for the sharing of knowledge in a *demosophic* society." And the author hopes that "a proper understanding of popular science will help us do that." (p. 154)

This book is not about the diffusion of knowledge, but the struggle over meaning; the separation of professional expertise from public experience, the relationship between science and democracy; the legitimization of scientific enterprise. (p. 6). Basically the book is about the role, function and capabilities of popular science in shaping and guiding the social forces determining us.

The author has truly succeeded in conveying these profound insights and this book is highly recommended for all those interested in issues of science and society. It is a must for those involved in philosophy of science and science-religion issues.

Kuruville Pandikattu

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